

Industries of Ideas Project Technical Brief

Person-Centric AI Research Community Identification: Initial Seed Set Validation*

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Abstract

The Industries of Ideas approach to identifying Critical and Emerging Technologies (CET) such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) departs from traditional bibliometric methods. Conceptually, we shift what it means to call something a “research field.” Topic-forward approaches often begin by characterizing the content of a research field, then using dimension-reduced representations of that content that are typically derived from some form of topic model, to distinguish participants from non-participants. The framework described here reverses this order of operations. We begin by identifying researchers active in a particular field, and then treat demarcating the field’s boundaries and content as a problem of community finding. That change carries significant empirical and methodological implications that require initial validation steps. In what follows we address:

- how a person-centric conceptual framework informs the project’s data and analytic approach
- core research community finding logic, data and initial external validation efforts
- preliminary validation findings for a new, labeled AI researchers file, the “AI seed set” that provides training, test and validation inputs for network based deep learning models capable of identifying research communities in multiple critical and emerging technologies (CETs).

Introduction

Scientific fields, such as disciplines, are commonly defined by their topics of study and the typical methods and procedures those studies use(1).. This style of thinking underpins much work in research evaluation (2) and more recently the science of science (3). From that vantage, identifying AI, or any critical and emerging technology (CET) field, is about drawing boundaries among clusters

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of ideas – topics – and using evidence of attention to those to define whether a paper, patent, grant, or sometimes person is working in that field. In essence what makes a field like AI a field in this view is the fact that it addresses a coherent set of topics. Thus, people are AI researchers if they study AI topics

The Industries of Ideas approach is different. It defines fields in more fundamentally social terms as communities of people and organizations(4). These “invisible colleges” (5) are defined by collaborative networks, reliance on common inputs, similar ways of thinking and approaching problems (6), often fierce competition to produce similar outputs for overlapping audiences, and shared rules and expectations that help govern all those activities (7). In this view, defining AI, or any CET, is a question about who is and who is not a member of a recognizable social and professional community.

Thus, we focus on people, not on documents or concepts. We rely on network science tools and social science theory to characterize community membership, defining the boundaries of a field by asking “Who is an AI researcher?” At any given moment AI topics are the set of things AI researchers study (8).

In keeping with this conception, Industries of Ideas identifies investments in AI research and traces them through industries, employers, and jobs by anchoring data and analysis on people and their work(9, 10). This has several benefits for identifying CETs. First, it introduces a degree of stability because individual careers are often relatively long even as topics of study and methods change, making it possible to both describe and identify potential levers to influence the trajectory of knowledge development (11).

Second, it enables a technology agnostic approach to field identification anchored on long established findings about community dynamics (12, 13) and robust network methods for operationalizing them (14-16). Third, it provides a ready means to connect the abstract doings of fundamental research to the concrete, day-to-day details of work and the economy through the mobility of people. We “follow the people” to identify CET fields as a first step to identifying the impact research investments in those fields have on the workforce and the economy.

Methodological Overview.

Our research community identification process has three steps. The first requires some attention to the particularities of a given research area. The other two are independent of technology and driven by human social dynamics.

In Step 1 we develop a heuristic that can identify a distinctive, high consensus group of individuals that represents the core of the field of interest. Intuitively, this is similar to the way that an academic might scan an unfamiliar CV for signals that an unknown researcher is a “card carrying” member of their professional tribe. The signals themselves vary from field to field, but they often have to do with placing work in preferred venues, invitations to present in high profile places, grants from specific agencies, or other widely accepted markers of success and acceptance. Most communities have formal or informal gatekeepers, who other members rely on to help vet newcomers (17). In AI, we treat presentation at any of 21 peer reviewed conferences as signals of community membership. Table 1 lists those conferences.

The seed set of AI researchers we identify using conference proceeding authorship serves as the basis for our second step in community identification. There are many people who may contribute to the

Conference Title for Seed Set Identification
Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics
Association for Advancement of Artificial Intelligence Conference on Artificial Intelligence
Association for Computing Machinery Conference on Recommender Systems
Association for Computing Machinery International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management
Association for Computing Machinery Special Interest Group on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining
Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing
Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems
Conference on Uncertainty in Artificial Intelligence
Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers and Computer Vision Foundation Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Conference
Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers and Computer Vision Foundation Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision
Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers International Conference on Data Mining
International Association for Computing Machinery Special Interest Group on Information Retrieval Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval
International Conference on Computer Vision
International Conference on Learning Representations
International Conference on Machine Learning
International Conference on Principles of Knowledge Representation and Reasoning
International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence
International Joint Conference on Natural Language Processing
Joint Conference on Lexical and Computational Semantics
Joint International Conference on Computational Linguistics
Robotics: Science and Systems

Table 1. Conferences Defining AI Seed Set

field and apply the knowledge it produces in highly innovative ways who are not themselves in the field's core. They are unlikely to appear in the seed set. However, their work might nevertheless represent an important route for federal investments in AI and its applications to be evaluated. Part of what makes AI such an important and difficult to measure area is its broad applicability. Methods that seek to characterize the impact and dynamics of CETs must be able to identify the domains in which novel uses of such technologies are driving innovation.

We use network science and graph neural network models to accomplish that. Seed set authors represent known members of a community. Other researchers who are connected to them in various ways have an unknown status with regard to it. Connections among them might be social (evidenced by collaboration), attentional (evidenced by citation), or affinity-based (evidenced by semantic similarity) in any combination. We use a multi-dimension network structure to test and compare a variety of model architectures but all address variants of the same problem.

We have a set of researchers who we “label” as members of a technology community, AI. We also have a much larger set of researchers whose relationship to that community is unknown. But we can measure their concrete direct and indirect ties to its members. Our baseline intuition is that the more someone (a) collaborates with, (b) pays attention to and uses the work of, and/or (c) publishes research similar to AI scientists, the more likely they are to *be* an AI scientist regardless of conference participation.

Initial Seed Set Validation: Approach and Goals.

All this makes defining a reasonable heuristic to identify a seed set an essential analytic step. It is, along with validation, one of only two parts of the process intended to explicitly take the specificity of fields into account. Thus, it often requires a process of qualitative analysis and iterative testing that takes place in conversation with domain experts and with study of the contemporary context and historical evolution of the field. Our intention in defining a seed set is to select a heuristic and a data source that can be used at scale, reliably, with reasonable face validity for experts and laypeople alike.

The first validation step we undertake is to test whether the group of researchers we identify as an AI seed set has the basic features necessary for it to serve the purposes we need it to for the larger Industries of Ideas project. Robust CET classification tools may also yield numerous independent benefits.

Following the conceptual framework laid out above, our ongoing work pursues four seed set validation tasks.

- (1) *Checking robustness to data sources.* Identifying an accessible, scalable means to define, collect and process global scale data about a fast moving, quickly growing area of research that implicates many other fields, as well as public and private sector applications poses challenges. Testing the robustness of definitions to different data sources and ensuring the ability to update and integrate in a reliable manner is key.
- (2) *Ensuring “core” field coverage.* The fundamental purpose of the seed set is to provide a ground against which to test the potential community membership of more distant researchers whose status relative to the field being studied is unobserved and, perhaps, unobservable. Thus, it is essential that the members of the seed set accurately represent a recognizable community whose collective work “hangs together.”

- (3) *Testing network reach to adjacent domains.* For Industries of Ideas, the seed set is also a steppingstone. Concrete relationships between its members and other researchers define the scope of the field by setting the boundaries of the community which is its characteristic feature. In arenas like AI with broad and varied applications, accuracy requires that the seed set include some individuals who can serve as starting points for networks that reach into many different domains. Otherwise, we risk leaving significant blind spots and biases in downstream measures of impact.
- (4) *Assessing the appropriate balance between precision and recall.* There is a fundamental tension between the second and third ideas above. Overly prescriptive attention to accurate representation of a field’s core by too aggressively minimizing false positives in a seed set may bias results by underestimating the reach of research investments and their eventual impact. But an overly loose definition that admits of too many false positives may dilute the identified community to the point of meaninglessness, running the risk of dramatic overestimation of research investments and their effects.

Actual calculations of precision, recall and related statistics depend on the existence of gold standard ground truth datasets laden with true positives and true negatives. None exist here. If they did, this exercise would be unnecessary. We thus assess this balance empirically, recognizing that sensitivity analyses conducted at different thresholds will be essential. Perhaps more importantly tighter or looser seed set apertures may be appropriate to different measurement tasks and use cases. It also seems likely that appropriate thresholds will vary across CETs and will have to be identified empirically.

Data and Expectations.

We seek to identify a seed set of active AI researchers who comprise the core of a quickly evolving interdisciplinary field that promises to dramatically reshape discovery and innovation in many areas of science and technology. In 2024, Nobel Prizes in Physics and Chemistry were awarded for contributions in AI. Many other CETs also draw upon AI innovations. Thus, we shift from the abstract statements above, which are intended to apply to many different fields, to more specific expectations for AI.

Validation Task 1: Robustness to Data Sources.

In what follows we compare AI seed sets defined using two different corpora of large-scale bibliometric metadata, Elsevier’s Scival/Scopus data on conference proceedings from 2010-2021 and Digital Science’s Dimensions data for 2005-2025. The former was the basis for work conducted in the Industries of Ideas pilot project. The latter expands that initial effort (by adding additional years and validating the robustness of seed set definitions across multiple data sources.

Expectation. Our baseline expectation for validation is that applying the same methods to seed set identification across two different but largely comparable data sources should (a) yield qualitatively similar sets of researchers, and (b) begin to identify strengths and weaknesses of different data sources for different uses.

Validation Tasks 2-3

For more substantive validation tasks, we rely on two data sets collected via web scraping. The first contains basic information – name, affiliation, award citation, year of election - on 385 researchers

elected as fellows of the Association for the Advancement of Artificial Intelligence (AAAI) from 1990 to 2024. AAAI fellows are “ . . . individuals who have made significant, sustained contributions -- usually over at least a ten-year period – to the field of artificial intelligence.” AAAI fellows offer one validation test of the seed set’s coverage of the core of field defined as mid to late career researchers recognized by their peers as making substantial contributions. However, because of the 25 year time-period – during which AI went through multiple shifts in focus accompanied by periods of funding ‘winter’ over this period (18) – temporal affects may loom large. Regardless, strong coverage of AAAI fellows in the seed set will offer an early indication that we are moving in the right direction as regards task 2.

A second dataset contains similar public information about the 1,657 faculty, staff, students and external participants affiliated with 27 National Science Foundation (NSF) and US Department of Agriculture funded AI Institutes. It offers the potential for deeper initial insights into Tasks 2-4. The AI Institutes cover topics ranging from frontier machine learning to education, molecular manufacturing, environmental science, astronomy, childhood development, fundamental physics, rural health, resilient agriculture and social decision-making.

In other words, AI Institutes and their affiliates will vary in the extent of their direct engagement with the AI research community itself as opposed to the domains where it is applied. If the seed set definition we chose results in stronger coverage of the field’s core community, we would expect affiliates of those institutes with a more intensive domain science focus to be less well represented (task 2). However, if the seed set also includes domain experts in many fields (task 3) – especially those who can be identified as faculty in domain areas such as physics, biology, agriculture, health care, deision-science or education – all institutes should have some coverage.

Similarly, several of the institutes we examine separate their affiliates into teams, distinguishing between those working directly on the development of AI tools, those developing domain projects, those working on education and workforce development, community or policy outreach efforts or other initiatives. Further validation work can leverage such internal variation as well to offer qualitative assessments of the effectiveness of different model architectures.

Validation Task 4.

While we do not report findings in this brief, within and across AI institute variation coupled with natural language processing of the award summaries of AAAI fellows or the publication portfolios of fellows and institute affiliates can also aid in assessments of validation task 4. For instance, we might vary criteria for inclusion in the seed set tightening or loosening inclusion thresholds (number of conferences, number of years, or number of publications, for instance) and testing the results against validation data to determine how varied seed set definitions shift the balance of coverage across more domain science oriented and more purely AI-focused institutes and affiliates. In later project phases where similar tests to assess parameters for semi-supervised classifiers will loom large, a similar logic will guide aspects of model development.

Initial Validation Findings.

Assessing Robustness to Data Sources (Task 1)

Figure 1 presents annual trends in the cumulative count of researchers included in the seed set defined using Elsevier and Digital Science data for the period during which those two data sources overlap, 2010-2021. Over that common observation period the two data sources are highly concurrent

with Elsevier data identifying 88,798 unique authors and Dimensions identifying 88,673 a difference of 0.14%.

As expected, the qualitative trends are also very similar. New seed set inclusions are defined by first observations of an author on a piece published in the proceedings of any conference listed in Table 1. Both data derived from Elsevier’s corpus and from Dimensions corpus indicates a period of significant but stable growth (<10,000 people per year) early in our timeframe. In 2018, the year after a seminal paper, 2017’s “Attention is all you need” (19) – which is widely credited with ushering in the transformer architecture that underpins current Large Language Models – there appears to have been an inflection point with the rate of growth in both lines accelerating in the final few years of Figure 1’s observation period.

Figure 1. Cumulative count of authors on papers published in conference proceedings associated with the international AI and Machine Learning conferences Identified in Table 1. Data drawn from Elsevier’s Scival/Scopus metadata corpus (Blue) and Digital Science’s Dimensions metadata corpus (Orange).

Figure 2, which presents the cumulative trend for the full, 2005-2025, Dimensions AI seed author dataset also highlights that 2018 transition as well as a second inflection point in 2022, the year that OpenAI publicly released ChatGPT 3.5. The 2005-2025 period spans the contemporary “deep learning” era of AI research, which can plausibly be dated to the 2006 publication of Hinton, Osindero and Teh’s (20) method for unsupervised layer-wise pretraining of deep neural network architectures. Although neural network methods have a much longer history, the 2006 Hinton et al paper and the 2009 introduction of the ImageNet infrastructure by Fei Fei Li and colleagues are widely credited with sparking the contemporary deep learning research. Similarly, the 2012 AlexNet large scale visual representation challenge result reported by Krizhevsky, Sutskever and Hinton (21) is commonly taken to mark the start of the subsequent deep neural networks application boom (22, 23).

We observe 216,025 global AI authors of whom 39,606 (18.3%) ever published a paper over a US-based institutional affiliation. All told, preliminary results for validation task 1 suggest that this seed set definition is both fairly robust to different underlying data sources and capable of capturing aggregate trends that accord with commonly held beliefs about recent milestone events AI’s evolution.

Cumulative Dimensions AI seed researchers

Complete Dimensions Seed Set Timeframe: 2005-2025

Figure 2. Cumulative count of unique AI “seed set” authors who published at least one paper in conference proceedings associated with the international AI and Machine Learning conferences listed in Table 1 archived by the Dimensions metadata corpus. Blue circles highlight two apparent inflection points in the cumulative rate of growth, 2018 marks a period of acceleration following the 2017 publication of “Attention is All You Need”, 2022 marks a second transition point following the release of GPT 3.5,

Assessing First Order Validity & Fitness for Purpose (Tasks 2-4)

To assess the first order validity of the seed set we define, we turn to two validation datasets collected from public, online sources via webscraping. The first, AAAI fellows, represents one view of the high consensus academic “core” of the field, at least as understood in terms of high-profile researchers. The second, affiliates of AI and USDA funded AI research institutes represents a more diffuse and challenging mix of people from a wide range of fields and functional areas who are none-the-less directly and publicly associated with large scale federal investments in AI research.

Matching Method. To assess the presence of AAAI fellows and NSF AI Institute Affiliates in the Dimensions AI seed set, we collected the full portfolio of publications from any source for AI seed set members to capture time varying affiliation information. After cleaning and standardizing text strings, we implemented a first pass multi-stage string matching algorithm conditioned on the presence of a common affiliation reported on a publication within a three-year window of either AAAI fellow election or observation of AI institute affiliation. The algorithm blocks on affiliation institution and last name, then conducts a full string match, followed by a last name and first initial

match, followed by a fuzzy (Jaro-Winkler) match.

We define “high confidence” matches as those where a single seed set record matched a single validation dataset record at either the full string, last name - first initial, or fuzzy threshold >0.85 level while meeting both temporal and affiliation conditions. Ambiguous matches are those where multiple candidate records matched with high confidence. Ambiguities for this small validation dataset were resolved initially by appeal to topic, venue, and affiliation information from authors’ full publication records and by web searches where such records were inconsistent or insufficient.

Figure 3. “Validation funnel” for AI Institute affiliates and AAAI fellows highlights match rates for each external validation source across four stages of the matching process. Identification of an affiliation organization (“Org Mapped”) in Dimensions metadata, identification of one or more individual match candidates within that organization based on last name blocking (“Candidate bearing”) resolution of a single, best, researcher match from among those candidates (“Researcher resolved”) and the presence of that resolved Dimensions researcher ID in the AI Seed Set. All percentages are calculated relative to “Raw Source Rows”.

We first match both AAAI fellows and AI institute affiliates to the full Dimensions corpus and then, via the resulting researcher id, to the seed set authors represented in Figure 2. Figure 3 summarizes the “matching funnel” for each of our two external validation data sets highlighting the stages of our process and match rates for each stage on the way to an overall initial seed set match for each source.

AAAI fellows are, not surprisingly more strongly represented in the Dimensions corpus, suffering the largest decline (to an 83% match rate) at the organizational matching stage. That decrease is largely attributable to often decades old affiliations (see following section). AI Institute Affiliates, in contrast see the greatest decline at the match candidate identification stage (a drop from 93% to 79%). This decline is primarily driven by the presence of a large number of staff members, industry and community affiliates and external advisors as well as students and trainees. These institute affiliates often either do not have or have not yet established the publication records necessary to

cement their presence in a primarily academic metadata source such as Dimensions.

The initial seed set match rates presented in Figure 3 – 209 AAAI Fellows (54%) and 495 AI Institute Affiliates (30%) – are artificially deflated by age in the former case and by the presence of many affiliates who we would not expect to match in the latter case. Figure 3’s overall match rates should thus be taken as a lower bound that tells us more about the process than the outcome, which is explored in more detail in subsequent sections.

AAAI Fellows.

Across 25 years of elected cohorts, 54% (209) of AAAI fellows appear in the seed set with high confidence matches. However, this relatively low rate is deceiving. The earliest cohorts of fellows were elected in 1990. This award is targeted at researchers who have made at least 10 years of sustained significant contributions to the field, which means that those elected in 1990 must have been mature, contributing scholars by 1980 and many were likely working actively earlier than that, in the 1970s, a period now 40-50 years removed from the observation period in which our seed set is defined. Many early fellows are listed as deceased on the award website, with dates of passing that precede our observation period. In other words, the denominator for the overall match rate is likely significantly inflated.

To remedy this situation, Figure 4 presents match rates for 5-year time blocks. Perhaps due to time lags, career dynamics, aging and changes in the field’s substantive focus over the last five decades, match rates are substantially better in recent time periods that roughly correspond with the deep learning and transformer/LLM eras that our observation period is designed to capture. The lowest match rates (31.4 and 54.2%) fall in the earliest cohorts, which, due to dating issues for very early inductees, are also very large. The period for which we define the seed set, and the periods of its highest growth see high confidence matches topping out at 91.4% and comfortably above 80% for all but the most recent cohort.

The expansion of that cohort’s size appears to have brought with it a larger number of researchers from outside academia, which may help account for the somewhat surprising decline in the most recent cohort’s match rate to a still respectable 71.7%.

More detailed analyses of the most recent cohorts are proceeding but the question posed in our second validation task - “Does a seed set derived from AI and machine learning conferences offer sufficient coverage of the ‘core’ of the field’ as represented by AAAI fellows to provide a useful labeled starting point for person centric expansion?” – appears to be answerable in the affirmative

NSF AI Institutes.

Affiliates of the NSF AI Institutes offer another, more nuanced view of the validity of our seed set. They also highlight the need for and challenges of the model expansion phase these labeled data support. Recall that our validation Task 3 shifts focus to assess the ability of a labeled seed set to identify relevant researchers in AI adjacent fields. Such “AI-enabled” research is of great potential interest for the Industries of Ideas use case because it may make significant domain and economic contributions with consequent broad effects on workforce, jobs, earnings and skills but not directly shape the pace or direction of innovation in AI technology itself.

Likewise, validation Task 4 offers hints as to how such a seed set, coupled with external validation data such as those we draw from funded AI institute affiliates can enable tuning of models and methods to achieve balances of precision and recall suitable to address different substantive questions and use cases ranging from narrowly focused analyses of core AI innovations to much broader

Figure 4. Match rates by cohort for AAAI fellows.

questions about applications of AI tools and methods across a wide range of science and technology domains.

Table 2 highlights these possibilities and provides greater insight into the seemingly low initial match rate reported in Figure 3 by reporting institute specific seed set match rates for 27 NSF and USDA AI institutes.

Unlike AAAI fellows, the affiliates of these institutes play many disparate roles including faculty, administrative, technical, and teaching staff, students and trainees at various levels, and external advisors of multiple types. Many of those (e.g. administrative staff, community representatives) would not be expected to pursue research in any field, let alone to publish in AI conference proceedings. Other affiliates, for instance, undergraduate and graduate students, might eventually do so but may be at early stages in their careers and yet to produce published papers.

As a result, Table 2 presents two sets of match rates, one for all affiliates and another for the subset of affiliates for whom at least one potential match candidate could be identified in the Dimensions corpus. For each institute the table also presents counts and percentages of listed affiliates for whom any potential match candidates could be identified. The latter offers a rough indicator of the extent to which a given institute’s listed affiliates are comprised of actively publishing academic researchers.

We begin by returning to the validation task that animated the AAAI fellows analysis, Task 2. Table 2 is ordered descending by all affiliate match rates. Consider the titles of the institutes as you read down the first column. Institutes with the highest overall match rates are also those closest to current common-sense notions of the topics of AI research; Machine Learning foundations and learning enabled system optimization. A second tier of match rates focuses on the integration of core

AI tools such as natural language and speech processing with practical problems such as education for developmentally challenged children, decision-making, cybersecurity, and cognitive science.

Institute Name	N Affiliates	Nw/ Match Candidates	Nin Seed Set	%w/ Match Candidates	Match Rate (Affiliates)	Match Rate (Candidates)
AI Institute: Institute for Foundations of Machine Learning	45	39	30	86.7%	66.7%	76.9%
AI Institute for Learning-Enabled Optimization at Scale (TILOS)	45	37	27	82.2%	60.0%	73.0%
AI Institute for Future Edge Networks and Distributed Intelligence (AI-EDGE)	60	51	33	85.0%	55.0%	64.7%
AI Institute for Agent-based Cyber Threat Intelligence and Operation	46	38	25	82.6%	54.3%	65.8%
AI Institute for Societal Decision Making (AI-SDM)	43	31	21	72.1%	48.8%	67.7%
AI Institute for Transforming Education for Children with Speech and Language Processing Challenges	38	30	18	78.9%	47.4%	60.0%
AI Institute for Artificial and Natural Intelligence	59	53	26	89.8%	44.1%	49.1%
AI Institute for Edge Computing Leveraging Next Generation Networks (Athena)	28	26	12	92.9%	42.9%	46.2%
AI Institute for Advances in Optimization	52	41	21	78.8%	40.4%	51.2%
AI Institute for Intelligent CyberInfrastructure with Computational Learning in the Environment (ICICLE)	47	41	18	87.2%	38.3%	43.9%
AI Institute for Land, Economy, Agriculture & Forestry (AI-LEAF)	62	57	23	91.9%	37.1%	40.4%
AI Institute for Collaborative Assistance and Responsive Interaction for Networked Groups (AI-CARING)	74	67	27	90.5%	36.5%	40.3%
AI Institute for Resilient Agriculture (AIIRA)	56	48	20	85.7%	35.7%	41.7%
Institute for Agricultural AI for Transforming Workforce and Decision Support (AgAID)	86	71	30	82.6%	34.9%	42.3%
AI Institute in Dynamic Systems	39	30	13	76.9%	33.3%	43.3%
Artificial Intelligence Materials Institute (AI-MI)	15	15	5	100.0%	33.3%	33.3%
AI Institute for Engaged Learning	77	53	25	68.8%	32.5%	47.2%
AI Institute: Institute for Student-AI Teaming	78	63	24	80.8%	30.8%	38.1%
NSF-Simons AI Institute for the Sky (SkAI Institute)	68	61	19	89.7%	27.9%	31.1%
AI Institute for Inclusive Intelligent Technologies for Education (INVITE)	48	38	12	79.2%	25.0%	31.6%
NSF-Simons AI Institute for Cosmic Origins	86	63	19	73.3%	22.1%	30.2%
AI Institute: Planning: AI Institute for Rural Health, Wellness, and Resilience	5	4	1	80.0%	20.0%	25.0%
Molecule Maker Lab Institute (MMLI): An AI Institute for Molecular Discovery, Synthetic Strategy, and Manufacturing	65	39	11	60.0%	16.9%	28.2%
AI Institute for Adult Learning and Online Education (ALOE)	106	69	10	65.1%	9.4%	14.5%
AI Institute: AI Research Institute for Fundamental Interactions	197	157	18	79.7%	9.1%	11.5%
Artificial Intelligence for Future Agricultural Resilience, Management, and Sustainability (AIFS)	32	17	2	53.1%	6.3%	11.8%
AI Institute: Artificial Intelligence for Environmental Sciences (AI2ES)	100	55	5	55.0%	5.0%	9.1%
Total	1657	1294	495	78.1%	29.9%	38.3%

Table 2. Institute specific match rates for 27 NSF and USDA Funded AI institutes. Match rates are presented relate to total affiliates and relative to affiliates with at least one same institution same last name match candidate. For each institute the table also presents the count and percent of total affiliates for whom any potential match candidates could be identified in the Dimensions metadata corpus, a rough indicator of the extent to which affiliate lists are made up of active academic researchers.

These domains of study deeply implicate core AI topics. They also engage decidedly AI adjacent, and increasingly AI enabled fields – such as linguistics, neuroscience, and cryptography – where researchers may make sophisticated use of AI tools and perhaps collaborate with core AI researchers but may be less likely themselves to contribute to work that results in publications in highly competitive AI or machine learning conferences.

At the bottom of the table, where match rates are the lowest, AI institutes are more directly focused on advancing specific agendas for domain science fields or societal concerns. In these cases, we would expect fewer affiliates to participate in AI-specific conferences and thus to be included in our seed set. However, we would also expect that they might be in the vanguard of their fields in using new AI tools, more likely to collaborate with AI seed set scientists, cite recent AI papers, and rely on AI more extensively in their own writing. Thus, it is precisely these scientists that we would hope to capture with semi-supervised model-based expansions using the seed set as a labeled group.

These institutes are also among those with the largest affiliate groups and the lowest percentages of affiliates with potential match candidates. Institutes such as the AI Institute for Adult Learning and Online Education, Artificial Intelligence for Future Agricultural Resilience, Management and Sustainability, and Artificial Intelligence for Environmental Sciences have very low match rates because they list many non-academic affiliates working in community engagement, extension-style outreach or advisory roles. Many of the affiliated academics work in research domains – such as education research – where AI tools are less commonly used than they are in areas such as computational linguistics or neuroscience that characterize higher match rate domains.

This sort of variation addresses the questions raised by our validation tasks 3 and 4. First, note that while some of the institute specific match rates are very low (in some cases in the single digits), none are zero. A social, person-centered and research community-based approach anchored on a seed set that does an effective job of capturing core areas of AI itself also provides starting points for network-based expansion models across the very wide range of domain areas represented in these institutes.

Figure 3 concretizes this idea by presenting the mission statements of four AI institutes that vary in how they integrate AI. Institutes with the lowest match rates (right) seek to turn AI tools toward forwarding work in environmental science and astronomy respectively. They are not advancing AI itself or aiming to develop general applications as is the case with the foundational machine learning models institute’s mission on the left.

In the domain science examples, most research affiliates are astronomers and physicists, or environmental and geoscientists. They are members of those research communities seeking to use AI, not core members of the AI research community itself. It is thus no surprise that few appear in our seed set. But, by virtue of their affiliations and participation in institutes supported by AI research investments we would expect them to be drawn closer to the AI research community in ways that are measurable under the Industries of Ideas framework. As a result, appropriately architected models can learn to distinguish them from their peers to enable a more complete assessment of the role AI plays in science and the role that AI research investments play in training the people who go on to innovate in jobs across the economy.

In other words, what may appear at first like a low overall match rate against the AI Institute affiliates validation set (all affiliates average 33.5%, faculty subset average 45.3%) reveals exactly what we would expect to see if the seed set is working as expected. That is a pattern of strong coverage of core AI areas with less comprehensive coverage as the role of AI researchers in the institutes shifts toward supporting the intellectual agendas of other domain communities (validation task 2) coupled with clear and sometimes substantial ‘footholds’ in every domain where NSF has funded an institute (validation task 3).

The social decision-making institute in the center of Figure 3 represents a middle ground that is visible because its website presents its affiliates organized into four teams. Those are focused on artificial intelligence, cognitive & behavioral science, disaster management & public health, and education & outreach. Though the overall match rate to the center as a whole is relatively low, the seed set captures 2/3 of members (66.6%) of this institutes designated artificial intelligence team. It also includes two members each of the cognitive and behavioral science team and disaster management and public health team. It does not include anyone from the education and outreach group. Once again, this time at a micro, within institute level, initial validation work suggests that the seed set works as expected.

The features of NSF AI institutes that make them useful for validation of the seed set also explain why they will offer a useful ground for establishing appropriate thresholds (task 4) and for the model development work to come. In both cases variations in parameters can be applied and tested against the institutes validation data to see how they fare. If, for instance, tightening the seed set increases match rates for core AI institutes at the top of Table 2 at the expense of losing the footholds currently found in more domain-oriented institutes currently arrayed at the bottom the tradeoff may prove too much for project goals. Similarly, a model whose parameters or inputs lead it to identify every domain scientist associated with an institute as an AI researcher may be painting with too broad a brush, while one that cannot successfully distinguish between AI institute affiliated

Figure 5. Mission Statements for Four NSF AI Institutes arranged by general orientation with three match rates. “All Affiliates” is relative the total number of affiliates listed on the institute website, “Match Candidates” is relative to the number of affiliates for whom at least one potentially viable matching candidate could be identified in the Dimensions metadata corpus and “Identified Faculty” is relative to the number of affiliates who could be positively identified as faculty members based on job titles and institute roles (e.g. PI) listed in affiliate information or collected via supplemental web searches.

domain scientists and their peers who are not connected to this research community may leave both important research investments and useful measures of their downstream impact on the table.

Conclusion.

The Industries of Ideas project’s framework for identifying critical and emerging technologies, such as AI, and tracing their effects on regional workforce, employers, jobs, education and skills depends upon two conceptual shifts. First, we conceptualize research fields as social and organizational communities, fields in the sense the term is used by organizational theorists and management researchers: recognizable social or economic domains characterized by shared norms, formal and informal “rules of the game” and networks of relationships that shape their workings, dynamics and outputs.(24-26)

Second, we shift our analytic emphasis for the purposes of modelling and measurement. Instead of using the contents of a field’s work to define its boundaries and identify its participants, we take a person-centric approach. That work draws on social science theories and network science tools to identify the sets of people who constitute the “invisible college” of AI researchers. Our emphasis on networks and individual mobility across organizations makes careers and connections the primary mechanism for the transmission and use of new ideas (27) Our desire to capture the effects of investments in innovation and training at the core of the field of AI *and* across the technology’s already broad and growing areas of application requires that we model and characterize an “AI research community” that reaches into the full range of domains where AI enabled research and research training is having effects.

We are mobilizing deep graph neural network models to help accomplish that goal, but such models require high quality training data. This technical brief has taken initial steps to demonstrate that a technology specific labeled set of researchers identified using expert generated definitions of and validated against public data can be robustly identified across multiple data sources, plausibly identify core academic researchers across a relatively long time frame spanning the current “era” of AI, capture reasonable starting points for modeling across a broad range of domain applications, and demonstrate a process for establishing a technology agnostic pipeline to identify and validate research communities of interest at with the potential to tune models to precision and recall thresholds suitable to more and less broadly focused use cases.

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